

Synthesis, spectral and biological investigation of arsenic(III) with [3-(2'-hydroxyphenyl)-5-(4'-substituted phenyl)pyrazolines] and *N*-aryl dithiocarbamate

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Manuscript received online 02 July 2013, revised 05 August 2013, accepted 19 August 2013

Abstract : A series of biological active mixed ligand complexes of arsenic(III) of the type $\text{AsCl}(\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_2\text{OX})(\text{S}_2\text{NC}_7\text{H}_5\text{X}')$ and $\text{As}(\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_2\text{OX})_2(\text{S}_2\text{NC}_7\text{H}_5\text{X}')$ where $\text{X} = -\text{H}, -\text{CH}_3, -\text{OCH}_3$ and $-\text{Cl}$; $\text{X}' = -\text{CH}_3, -\text{OCH}_3$ have been prepared and studied. These complexes has been made by reacting the dichloroarsenic(III) pyrazolines and chloroarsenic(III) dipyrazoline with sodium salt of (*N*-aryl dithiocarbamate) in 1 : 1 molar ratio in anhydrous benzene at elevated temperature and characterized by elemental analysis (C, H, N, S, Cl and As), molecular weight measurement, UV-Visible, near and far IR, multinuclear NMR (^1H and ^{13}C) spectroscopy and FAB mass spectrometry. A distorted trigonal bipyramidal and distorted octahedral structure around central As^{III} atom for $\text{AsCl}(\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_2\text{OX})(\text{S}_2\text{NC}_7\text{H}_5\text{X}')$ and $\text{As}(\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_2\text{OX})_2(\text{S}_2\text{NC}_7\text{H}_5\text{X}')$ has been suggested respectively. Antibacterial and antifungal potential of dichloroarsenic(III) pyrazolines, chloroarsenic(III) dipyrazolines and these newly synthesized derivatives are also discussed.

Keywords : Arsenic(III), pyrazolines, antimicrobial activity.

Introduction

Arsenic compounds had a long Janus type interaction with humanity. On one hand, they have been extensively utilized, but on the other hand, their poisonous properties have caused misery and many deaths. Because of their significant properties, arsenic compounds have been used as therapeutic agents for more than 2400 years¹. In early times of the East, a mixture of orpiment, slaked lime (CaO), and water was favored as a depilatory. Moreover, a paste of realgar was recommended by Hippocrates for treatment of ulcers. Arsenic compounds have also been used to treat the plague, malaria and cancer. Arsenides and arsenic salts were key ingredients in antiseptics, antispasmodics, antiperiodics, caustics, cholagogues, hematinics, sedatives, and tonics. Approximately 60 different arsenic preparations have been developed and distributed during the history^{2,3}.

The pyrazolines are an important class of heterocyclic compounds, which are used in industries as dyes, antioxidants in lubricating oils⁴ and in agriculture as catalyst for carboxylation reactions as well as inhibitors for plant growth⁵⁻⁷. In day to day life, pyrazolines are extensively

used in photography⁸. Reports are also available for a large number of other hydroxyl phenyl substituted heterocycles, which are used as agrochemical fungicides⁹ and anticonvulsant agents¹⁰. Complexation behavior of [3-(2'-hydroxyphenyl)-5-(4'-X-substituted phenyl)-pyrazolines] and substituted pyrazolines with arsenic, antimony and bismuth have been investigated in our laboratories¹¹⁻¹³. We have also investigated the complexation behavior and antimicrobial potential of 3-(2'-hydroxyphenyl)-5-(4'-X-phenyl pyrazolines) and substituted pyrazolines with tin(IV), organotin(IV), diorganotin(IV) and triorganotin(IV)¹⁴⁻¹⁸.

In the continuation of our previous work, it was thought worthwhile to study the complexation behavior of arsenic(III), antimony(III) and bismuth(III) with 3-(2'-hydroxyphenyl)-5-(4'-substituted phenyl pyrazolines) and *N*-aryl dithiocarbamate.

In the present paper we describe the synthesis, spectral and antimicrobial studies of mixed ligand complexes of arsenic(III) with 3-(2'-hydroxyphenyl)-5-(4'-X-phenyl pyrazolines) and *N*-aryl dithiocarbamate.

Results and discussion

All the complexes are pale to brown colored solid, non-hygroscopic and stable at room temperature. These are soluble in common organic solvents (methanol, acetone, benzene and chloroform) and coordinating solvents (THF, DMSO and DMF). The molecular weight measurement indicates monomeric nature of the compound. The elemental analysis (As metal, C, N, H, S and Cl) data are in accordance with the stoichiometry proposed

for respective compounds.

We have already discussed the structural characteristics of arsenic(III)tripyrazolates in our previous publication¹³. Therefore we will focus on the structural changes observed after coordination of *N*-aryl dithiocarbamate to the arsenic(III).

Infrared spectra :

The infrared spectra of the complexes are recorded in the range 4000–50 cm⁻¹ and are summarized in Table 2.

Table 1. Synthetic and analytical data for [AsCl(C₁₅H₁₂N₂OX)(S₂NC₇H₅X')] and [As(C₁₅H₁₂N₂OX)₂(S₂NC₇H₅X')]

Compd. No.	Compd.	Yield (%)	M.p. (°C)	Mol. wt. Found (Calcd.)	Elemental analysis (%) :					
					As	C	H	N	S	Cl
1	As(C ₁₅ H ₁₃ N ₂ O)	80	98	529	14.11	52.09	3.92	7.89	12.00	6.67
	(S ₂ NC ₇ H ₅ CH ₃)Cl			(529.50)	(14.16)	(52.12)	(3.96)	(7.93)	(12.08)	(6.70)
2	As(C ₁₅ H ₁₂ N ₂ OCH ₃)	77	112	542	13.75	52.87	4.20	7.69	11.75	6.49
	(S ₂ NC ₇ H ₅ CH ₃)Cl			(543.50)	(13.79)	(52.98)	(4.23)	(7.72)	(11.77)	(6.53)
3	As(C ₁₅ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₂ CH ₃)	86	110	559	13.35	51.40	4.09	7.45	11.42	6.30
	(S ₂ NC ₇ H ₅ CH ₃)Cl			(559.50)	(13.40)	(51.47)	(4.11)	(7.50)	(11.43)	(6.34)
4	As(C ₁₅ H ₁₂ N ₂ OCl)	70	108	562	13.20	48.87	3.50	7.41	11.30	12.53
	(S ₂ NC ₇ H ₅ CH ₃)Cl			(564.00)	(13.29)	(48.93)	(3.54)	(7.44)	(11.34)	(12.58)
5	As(C ₁₅ H ₁₃ N ₂ O)	84	102	544	13.71	50.51	3.79	7.61	11.71	5.47
	(S ₂ NC ₇ H ₅ OCH ₃)Cl			(545.50)	(13.74)	(50.59)	(3.84)	(7.69)	(11.73)	(5.50)
6	As(C ₁₅ H ₁₂ N ₂ OCH ₃)	75	131	558	13.35	51.44	4.07	7.48	11.39	6.29
	(S ₂ NC ₇ H ₅ OCH ₃)Cl			(559.50)	(13.40)	(51.47)	(4.11)	(7.50)	(11.43)	(6.34)
7	As(C ₁₅ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₂ CH ₃)	80	128	574	13.07	50.08	3.97	7.25	11.09	6.10
	(S ₂ NC ₇ H ₅ OCH ₃)Cl			(575.50)	(13.03)	(50.04)	(3.99)	(7.29)	(11.12)	(6.16)
8	As(C ₁₅ H ₁₂ N ₂ OCl)	71	138	580	12.87	47.55	3.40	7.22	11.06	6.01
	(S ₂ NC ₇ H ₅ OCH ₃)Cl			(580.00)	(12.93)	(47.58)	(3.44)	(7.24)	(11.03)	(6.12)
9	As(C ₁₅ H ₁₃ N ₂ O) ₂	80	137	730	10.18	62.30	4.62	9.50	8.70	–
	(S ₂ NC ₇ H ₅ CH ₃)			(731.00)	(10.25)	(62.38)	(4.65)	(9.57)	(8.75)	–
10	As(C ₁₅ H ₁₂ N ₂ OCH ₃) ₂	67	120	758	9.81	63.19	4.97	9.19	8.40	–
	(S ₂ NC ₇ H ₅ CH ₃)			(759.00)	(9.88)	(63.24)	(5.00)	(9.22)	(8.43)	–
11	As(C ₁₅ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₂ CH ₃) ₂	83	124	790	9.40	60.64	4.75	8.79	8.01	–
	(S ₂ NC ₇ H ₅ CH ₃)			(791.00)	(9.48)	(60.68)	(4.80)	(8.84)	(8.09)	–
12	As(C ₁₅ H ₁₂ N ₂ OCl) ₂	76	112	800	9.31	57.10	3.98	8.70	7.97	8.79
	(S ₂ NC ₇ H ₅ CH ₃)			(800.00)	(9.37)	(57.00)	(4.00)	(8.75)	(8.00)	(8.87)
13	As(C ₁₅ H ₁₃ N ₂ O) ₂	77	131	746	10.00	61.09	4.51	9.30	8.51	–
	(S ₂ NC ₇ H ₅ OCH ₃)			(747.00)	(10.04)	(61.04)	(4.55)	(9.37)	(8.56)	–
14	As(C ₁₅ H ₁₂ N ₂ OCH ₃) ₂	84	124	758	9.79	63.10	4.97	9.15	8.39	–
	(S ₂ NC ₇ H ₅ OCH ₃)			(760.00)	(9.86)	(63.15)	(5.00)	(9.21)	(8.42)	–
15	As(C ₁₅ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₂ CH ₃) ₂	80	109	805	9.25	59.41	4.68	8.60	7.89	–
	(S ₂ NC ₇ H ₅ OCH ₃)			(807.00)	(9.29)	(59.47)	(4.70)	(8.67)	(7.93)	–
16	As(C ₁₅ H ₁₂ N ₂ OCl) ₂	74	122	815	9.11	55.80	3.90	8.50	7.80	8.61
	(S ₂ NC ₇ H ₅ OCH ₃)			(816.00)	(9.19)	(55.88)	(3.92)	(8.57)	(7.84)	(8.70)

Table 2. IR spectral data (cm⁻¹) for [AsCl(C₁₅H₁₂N₂OX)(S₂NC₇H₅X')] and [As(C₁₅H₁₂N₂OX)₂(S₂NC₇H₅X')]

Compd. No.	v(N-H)	v(C=N)	v(C=S)	v(C-O)	v(C-S)	v(As-O)	v(As-N)	v(As-Cl)	v(As-S)
1	3436	1624 1496	1035	–	985	532	441	379	324
2	3430	1620 1540	1030	–	982	510	445	353	331
3	3392	1621 1499	1025	1012	980	502	446	352	334
4	3394	1638 1533	1031	–	989	522	436	356	336
5	3452	1632 1545	1032	–	982	536	448	358	330
6	3449	1630 1540	1034	–	981	530	441	351	320
7	3443	1626 1512	1028	1011	982	526	440	360	325
8	3432	1620 1498	1034	–	980	502	442	354	332
9	3398	1621 1544	1030	–	983	508	438	–	334
10	3412	1620 1522	1025	–	981	507	436	–	332
11	3433	1615 1538	1031	1013	982	505	435	–	322
12	3420	1625 1543	1034	–	988	511	440	–	320
13	3431	1623 1541	1034	–	984	501	448	–	319
14	3429	1625 1545	1031	–	989	521	435	–	321
15	3422	1623 1496	1030	1011	984	539	436	–	326
16	3392	1622 1498	1032	–	987	507	430	–	320

All the complexes exhibit bands of medium intensity in the region 3449–3392 cm⁻¹ due to v(N-H) stretching vibrations and 1638–1615 cm⁻¹ due to v(C=N) stretching vibrations^{11–23}. The signal due to v(O-H) (originally present at ~3085 cm⁻¹ in the free pyrazolines) is completely disappeared from the spectra of the complexes^{11–23}. Compound **1-8** exhibit in the region of 379–351 cm⁻¹ due to v(As-Cl) stretching vibrations²⁴. The appearance of two new bands in the region 539–501 and 448–430 cm⁻¹ are assigned to v(As-O) and v(As-N) stretching vibrations respectively^{23,25}. The appearance of these two bands due to v(As-O) and v(As-N) and absence of hydroxyl band suggest that pyrazoline behave as mono basic bidentate ligand in these complexes^{11–23}. Strong intensity

bands in region 989–980 cm⁻¹, 1035–1025 cm⁻¹ and 1545–1496 cm⁻¹ due to v(C-S), v(C=S) and v(C-N) stretching vibrations respectively, indicating bidentate behavior of dithiocarbamate group in these complexes^{26–29}. The band of weak intensity at 336–319 cm⁻¹ is due to v(As-S) stretching vibration^{27–31}.

Multinuclear NMR spectroscopy :

The ¹H NMR chemical shifts of these compounds are listed in Table 3. In ¹H NMR spectra, all the complexes were observed as multiplet in the region δ 7.9–6.3 ppm due to the presence of aromatic protons of pyrazoline and *N*-aryl dithiocarbamate^{11–22,26–29,32}. The peak at δ 5.5–5.1 ppm assigned to N-H group suggesting the non involvement of N-H group in the bond formation^{11–22,32}.

The skeletal protons of 5 membered ring are observed at δ 3.4–3.3 ppm as a triplet and at δ 2.5–2.0 as a doublet could be assigned to CH and CH₂ group respectively^{11–22,32}. The integration ratio corresponds well with the presence of one dithiocarbamate and two pyrazoline ligand in these complexes (Fig. 1).

The proton decoupled ¹³C NMR spectra (Table 3) of the complexes show all the important signals with reference to pyrazoline and *N*-aryl dithiocarbamate^{11–22,26–29,32}. The signal at δ 145.7–120.1 ppm as multiplet assigned to aromatic carbon^{11–22,32}. *N*-Aryl dithiocarbamate shows one characteristics band in the region δ 184.3–174.3 ppm

Fig. 1. ¹H NMR spectra of [(C₁₅H₁₃N₂O)As(S₂NC₇H₅CH₃)Cl].

Compd. No.	Compd.	¹ H NMR chemical shift (in δ ppm)	¹³ C NMR chemical shift (in δ ppm)
1	As(C ₁₅ H ₁₃ N ₂ O)(S ₂ NC ₇ H ₅ CH ₃)Cl	7.8–6.8 (13H, m, Ar-H) 5.1 (2H, s, NH) 3.6 (1H, t, CH) 2.3 (2H, d, CH ₂) 1.1 (3H, s, CH ₃)	184.3 (NCS ₂) 157.2 (C=N) 142.3–120.1 (Ar-C) 42.9 (CH) 20.9 (CH ₂) 13.8 (CH ₃)
2	As(C ₁₅ H ₁₂ N ₂ OCH ₃)(S ₂ NC ₇ H ₅ CH ₃)Cl	7.9–6.9 (12H, m, Ar-H) 5.5 (2H, t, NH) 3.4 (1H, t, CH) 2.5 (2H, d, CH ₂) 0.9 (6H, s, CH ₃)	181.3 (NCS ₂) 158.5 (C=N) 143.1–123.3 (Ar-C) 47.5 (CH) 28.7 (CH ₂) 13.8 (CH ₃)

Table-3 (contd.)

3	As(C ₁₅ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₂ CH ₃)(S ₂ NC ₇ H ₅ CH ₃)Cl	7.8–6.8 (12H, m, Ar-H)	181.7 (NCS ₂)
		5.5 (2H, s, NH)	159.9 (C=N)
		3.3 (1H, t, CH)	145.7–123.0 (Ar-C)
		2.0 (2H, d, CH ₂)	46.2 (CH)
		0.8 (3H, s, CH ₃)	28.1 (CH ₂)
		3.6 (3H, s, OCH ₃)	13.8 (CH ₃)
		51.5 (OCH ₃)	
4	As(C ₁₅ H ₁₂ N ₂ OCl)(S ₂ NC ₇ H ₅ CH ₃)Cl	7.8–6.3 (12H, m, Ar-H)	181.7 (NCS ₂)
		5.4 (2H, s, NH)	158.9 (C=N)
		3.4 (1H, t, CH)	145.7–123.0 (Ar-C)
		2.2 (2H, d, CH ₂)	46.2 (CH)
		0.9 (3H, s, CH ₃)	28.1 (CH ₂)
			13.8 (CH ₃)
5	As(C ₁₅ H ₁₃ N ₂ O)(S ₂ NC ₇ H ₅ OCH ₃)Cl	7.2–6.8 (13H, m, Ar-H)	174.3 (NCS ₂)
		5.1 (2H, s, NH)	157.2 (C=N)
		3.3 (1H, t, CH)	142.3–120.1 (Ar-C)
		2.3 (2H, d, CH ₂)	42.9 (CH)
		3.5 (3H, s, OCH ₃)	20.9 (CH ₂)
			51.5 (OCH ₃)
6	As(C ₁₅ H ₁₂ N ₂ OCH ₃)(S ₂ NC ₇ H ₅ OCH ₃)Cl	7.9–6.8 (12H, m, Ar-H)	181.3 (NCS ₂)
		5.4 (2H, s, NH)	158.5 (C=N)
		3.4 (1H, t, CH)	143.1–123.3 (Ar-C)
		2.5 (2H, d, CH ₂)	47.5 (CH)
		0.9 (3H, s, CH ₃)	28.7 (CH ₂)
		3.6 (3H, s, OCH ₃)	13.8 (CH ₃)
7	As(C ₁₅ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₂ CH ₃)(S ₂ NC ₇ H ₅ OCH ₃)Cl	7.8–6.8 (12H, m, Ar-H)	181.7 (NCS ₂)
		5.5 (2H, s, NH)	55.9 (C=N)
		3.3 (1H, t, CH)	145.7–123.0 (Ar-C)
		2.0 (2H, d, CH ₂)	46.2 (CH)
		3.6 (3H, s, OCH ₃)	28.1 (CH ₂)
			51.5 (OCH ₃)
8	As(C ₁₅ H ₁₂ N ₂ OCl)(S ₂ NC ₇ H ₅ OCH ₃)Cl	7.8–6.3 (12H, m, Ar-H)	181.7 (NCS ₂)
		5.3 (2H, s, NH)	155.9 (C=N)
		3.4 (1H, t, CH)	145.7–123.0 (Ar-C)
		2.2 (2H, d, CH ₂)	46.2 (CH)
		3.6 (3H, s, OCH ₃)	28.1 (CH ₂)
			51.5 (OCH ₃)
9	As(C ₁₅ H ₁₃ N ₂ O) ₂ (S ₂ NC ₇ H ₅ CH ₃)	7.5–6.7 (22H, m, Ar-H)	182.7 (NCS ₂)
		5.4 (3H, s, NH)	157.2 (C=N)
		3.4 (2H, t, CH)	143.2–120.1 (Ar-C)
		2.3 (4H, d, CH ₂)	42.8 (CH)
		0.9 (3H, s, CH ₃)	21.9 (CH ₂)
			13.8 (CH ₃)

Table-3 (contd.)

10	As(C ₁₅ H ₁₂ N ₂ OCH ₃) ₂ (S ₂ NC ₇ H ₅ CH ₃)	7.8–6.9 (20H, m, Ar-H)	182.3 (NCS ₂)
		5.5 (3H, s, NH)	159.5 (C=N)
		3.3 (2H, t, CH)	143.1–123.3 (Ar-C)
		2.4 (4H, d, CH ₂)	47.4 (CH)
		0.9 (9H, s, CH ₃)	28.6 (CH ₂)
			13.8 (CH ₃)
11	As(C ₁₅ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₂ CH ₃) ₂ (S ₂ NC ₇ H ₅ CH ₃)	7.8–6.7 (20H, m, Ar-H)	183.7 (NCS ₂)
		5.2 (3H, s, NH)	156.1 (C=N)
		3.3 (2H, t, CH)	145.7–123.0 (Ar-C)
		2.1 (4H, d, CH ₂)	46.2 (CH)
		0.8 (3H, s, CH ₃)	28.2 (CH ₂)
		3.5 (6H, s, OCH ₃)	13.9 (CH ₃)
12	As(C ₁₅ H ₁₂ N ₂ OCl) ₂ (S ₂ NC ₇ H ₅ CH ₃)	7.9–6.3 (20H, m, Ar-H)	183.7 (NCS ₂)
		5.1 (3H, s, NH)	157.9 (C=N)
		3.4 (2H, t, CH)	145.7–123.0 (Ar-C)
		2.2 (4H, d, CH ₂)	46.2 (CH)
		0.9 (3H, s, CH ₃)	28.1 (CH ₂)
			13.8 (CH ₃)
13	As(C ₁₅ H ₁₃ N ₂ O) ₂ (S ₂ NC ₇ H ₅ OCH ₃)	7.4–6.7 (22H, m, Ar-H)	174.3 (NCS ₂)
		5.4 (3H, s, NH)	146.3–126.1 (Ar-C)
		3.3 (2H, t, CH)	43.9 (CH)
		2.3 (4H, d, CH ₂)	21.9 (CH ₂)
		3.6 (3H, s, OCH ₃)	52.5 (OCH ₃)
14	As(C ₁₅ H ₁₂ N ₂ OCH ₃) ₂ (S ₂ NC ₇ H ₅ OCH ₃)	7.9–6.8 (20H, m, Ar-H)	179.3 (NCS ₂)
		5.3 (3H, s, NH)	158.2 (C=N)
		3.4 (2H, t, CH)	143.1–123.3 (Ar-C)
		2.5 (4H, d, CH ₂)	47.5 (CH)
		0.9 (6H, s, CH ₃)	28.7 (CH ₂)
		3.5 (3H, s, OCH ₃)	13.8 (CH ₃)
15	As(C ₁₅ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₂ CH ₃) ₂ (S ₂ NC ₇ H ₅ OCH ₃)	7.8–6.7 (20H, m, Ar-H)	181.7 (NCS ₂)
		5.5 (3H, s, NH)	158.9 (C=N)
		3.3 (2H, d, CH ₂)	145.7–123.0 (Ar-C)
		2.0 (4H, d, CH ₂)	46.2 (CH)
		3.6 (9H, s, OCH ₃)	28.1 (CH ₂)
			51.5 (OCH ₃)
16	As(C ₁₅ H ₁₂ N ₂ OCl) ₂ (S ₂ NC ₇ H ₅ OCH ₃)	7.9–6.7 (20H, m, Ar-H)	182.7 (NCS ₂)
		5.5 (2H, s, NH)	158.9 (C=N)
		3.4 (1H, d, CH ₂)	145.7–123.0 (Ar-C)
		2.3 (2H, d, CH ₂)	46.2 (CH)
		3.5 (3H, s, OCH ₃)	28.1 (CH ₂)
			51.5 (OCH ₃)

due to the presence of carbon of -NCS₂ group^{26–29} (Fig. 2).

Electronic spectra :

The electronic spectral data for [AsCl(C₁₅H₁₂N₂OX)-

Fig. 2. ^{13}C NMR spectra of $[(\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{13}\text{N}_2\text{O})\text{As}(\text{S}_2\text{NC}_7\text{H}_5\text{CH}_3)\text{Cl}]$.

$(\text{S}_2\text{NC}_7\text{H}_5\text{X}')$] and $[\text{As}(\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_2\text{OX})_2(\text{S}_2\text{NC}_7\text{H}_5\text{X}')]$ complexes are listed in Table 4. In all the arsenic(III) complexes, $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ and $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition due to pyrazoline moieties appear as a broad band in the range 249–240 nm^{19–22,33–34}. The second band at 311–305 nm is assigned to $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition in the NCS group of dithiocarbamate moiety^{26,28,29}. The third band of comparatively low intensity in the range 366–344 nm is attributed to ligand to metal d orbital transition²⁹.

FAB mass spectra :

The FAB mass spectra of all the complexes give a characteristic peak at $[\text{M}^+]$ along with other peak showing fragmentation (Fig. 3). The mass spectra of $[\text{As}(\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{13}\text{N}_2\text{O})(\text{S}_2\text{NC}_7\text{H}_5\text{CH}_3)\text{Cl}]$ and $[\text{As}(\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{13}\text{N}_2\text{O})_2(\text{S}_2\text{NC}_7\text{H}_5\text{CH}_3)]$ exhibited the molecular ion peak at m/z 529 and 731 respectively along with other fragment ions peak (Table 5).

Microbial assay :

The antibacterial activities of dichloroarsenic(III)-pyrazolines, chloroarsenic(III)dipyrazolines and two mixed ligand complexes of arsenic(III) were tested against

the bacterial species, *Bacillus subtilis*, *Pseudomonas sp.* and the antifungal activities were tested against *Aspergillus flavus* and *Penicillium chrysogenum*. The antimicrobial activity of some antibiotics were also tested and compared with dichloroarsenic(III)pyrazolines, chloroarsenic(III)dipyrazolines and two mixed ligand complexes of arsenic(III). The antiviral activity of the complexes was tested against Papaya ring spot virus. The results are listed in Table 6.

Comparison of the antimicrobial activities of chloroarsenic(III)pyrazolines and two mixed ligand complexes of arsenic(III) with some known antibiotics exhibit the following results :

(i) The complexes exhibit greater antibacterial effects towards *Bacillus subtilis* compared to chloroarsenic(III)-dipyrazolines, dichloroarsenic(III)pyrazolines and antibiotic Kanamycin (Fig. 5).

(ii) The complexes $[\text{AsCl}(\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_2\text{OX})(\text{S}_2\text{NC}_7\text{H}_5\text{X}')]$ and $[\text{As}(\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_2\text{OX})_2(\text{S}_2\text{NC}_7\text{H}_5\text{X}')]$ exhibit greater antibacterial effect towards *Pseudomonas sp.* compared to chloroarsenic(III)dipyrazolines, dichloroarsenic(III)-

Table 4. Electronic spectral data for $[\text{AsCl}(\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_2\text{OX})(\text{S}_2\text{NC}_7\text{H}_5\text{X}')] \text{ and } [\text{As}(\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_2\text{OX})_2(\text{S}_2\text{NC}_7\text{H}_5\text{X}')]$

Compd. No.	Compd.	Electronic spectral data (in nm)		
		(I) Pyrazoline	(II) Dithiocarbamate	(III) Ligand→Metal <i>d</i> orbital
1	$\text{As}(\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{13}\text{N}_2\text{O})(\text{S}_2\text{NC}_7\text{H}_5\text{CH}_3)\text{Cl}$	241	305	364–349
2	$\text{As}(\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_2\text{OCH}_3)(\text{S}_2\text{NC}_7\text{H}_5\text{CH}_3)\text{Cl}$	245	308	366–349
3	$\text{As}(\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_2\text{O}_2\text{CH}_3)(\text{S}_2\text{NC}_7\text{H}_5\text{CH}_3)\text{Cl}$	243	310	364–345
4	$\text{As}(\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_2\text{OCl})(\text{S}_2\text{NC}_7\text{H}_5\text{CH}_3)\text{Cl}$	249	311	364–344
5	$\text{As}(\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{13}\text{N}_2\text{O})(\text{S}_2\text{NC}_7\text{H}_5\text{OCH}_3)\text{Cl}$	240	306	361–347
6	$\text{As}(\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_2\text{OCH}_3)(\text{S}_2\text{NC}_7\text{H}_5\text{OCH}_3)\text{Cl}$	246	308	362–347
7	$\text{As}(\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_2\text{O}_2\text{CH}_3)(\text{S}_2\text{NC}_7\text{H}_5\text{OCH}_3)\text{Cl}$	243	305	362–347
8	$\text{As}(\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_2\text{OCl})(\text{S}_2\text{NC}_7\text{H}_5\text{OCH}_3)\text{Cl}$	241	307	364–345
9	$\text{As}(\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{13}\text{N}_2\text{O})_2(\text{S}_2\text{NC}_7\text{H}_5\text{CH}_3)$	248	311	365–349
10	$\text{As}(\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_2\text{OCH}_3)_2(\text{S}_2\text{NC}_7\text{H}_5\text{CH}_3)$	246	311	362–345
11	$\text{As}(\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_2\text{O}_2\text{CH}_3)_2(\text{S}_2\text{NC}_7\text{H}_5\text{CH}_3)$	248	306	364–349
12	$\text{As}(\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_2\text{OCl})_2(\text{S}_2\text{NC}_7\text{H}_5\text{CH}_3)$	241	308	364–349
13	$\text{As}(\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{13}\text{N}_2\text{O})_2(\text{S}_2\text{NC}_7\text{H}_5\text{OCH}_3)$	247	308	345–347
14	$\text{As}(\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_2\text{OCH}_3)_2(\text{S}_2\text{NC}_7\text{H}_5\text{OCH}_3)$	242	311	361–344
15	$\text{As}(\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_2\text{O}_2\text{CH}_3)_2(\text{S}_2\text{NC}_7\text{H}_5\text{OCH}_3)$	248	306	362–345
16	$\text{As}(\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_2\text{OCl})_2(\text{S}_2\text{NC}_7\text{H}_5\text{OCH}_3)$	241	311	362–345

Fig. 3. FAB mass spectra of $[(\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{13}\text{N}_2\text{O})\text{As}(\text{S}_2\text{NC}_7\text{H}_5\text{CH}_3)\text{Cl}]$.

pyrazolinates and antibiotic Kanamycin.

(iii) The complexes $[\text{AsCl}(\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_2\text{OX})(\text{S}_2\text{NC}_7\text{H}_5\text{X}')] \text{ and } [\text{As}(\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_2\text{OX})_2(\text{S}_2\text{NC}_7\text{H}_5\text{X}')] \text{ exhibit greater antifungal effect towards } \textit{Aspergillus flavus}$ (Fig. 4) and $\textit{Penicillium chrysogenum}$ compared to chloroarsenic(III)-

dipyrazolinates and Terbinafin.

(iv) Antiviral activity of the synthesized compounds show significant activity against Papaya ring spot virus and inhibition of about 75%.

It is noted that As^{III} complexes exhibit more or less

Table 5.
FAB mass fragmentation pattern of [As(C₁₅H₁₂N₂OX)(S₂NC₇H₅X')Cl]

Fragment ion formulae	<i>m/z</i>	
	Compound 1, X = -H and X' = -CH ₃	Compound 3, X = -OCH ₃ and X' = -CH ₃
[(C ₁₅ H ₁₂ N ₂ OX)AsCl(S ₂ NC ₇ H ₅ X')]•+	529	559
[(C ₆ H ₄ O)AsCl(S ₂ NC ₇ H ₅ X')]•+	384	384
[AsCl(S ₂ NC ₇ H ₅ CH ₃)]•+	292	292
(S ₂ CNHC ₆ H ₅ CH ₃)•+	182	182
(SCNC ₆ H ₅ CH ₃)•+	149	149
(CNHC ₆ H ₅ CH ₃)•+	117	117
(NHC ₆ H ₅ CH ₃)•+	105	105
(C ₆ H ₅ CH ₃)•+	91	91

FAB mass fragmentation pattern of [As(C₁₅H₁₂N₂OX)₂(S₂NC₇H₅X')]

Fragment ion formulae	<i>m/z</i>	
	Compound 1, X = -H and X' = -CH ₃	Compound 3, X = -OCH ₃ and X' = -CH ₃
[(C ₁₅ H ₁₂ N ₂ OX) ₂ As(S ₂ NC ₇ H ₅ X')]•+	731	761
[(C ₂₁ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₂ X)As(S ₂ NC ₇ H ₅ X')]•+	586	616
[(C ₁₅ H ₁₃ N ₂ O)As(S ₂ NC ₇ H ₅ CH ₃)]•+	494	494
[As(S ₂ NC ₇ H ₅ CH ₃)]•+	257	257
(S ₂ CNHC ₆ H ₅ CH ₃)•+	182	182
(SCNC ₆ H ₅ CH ₃)•+	149	149
(CNHC ₆ H ₅ CH ₃)•+	117	117
(NHC ₆ H ₅ CH ₃)•+	105	105
(C ₆ H ₅ CH ₃)•+	91	91

Fig. 4. Antifungal activity against *Aspergillus flavus*, (1) Terbinafin, (2) DMSO, (3) chloroarsenic(III)dipyrazolinates and (4) [(C₁₅H₁₃N₂O)₂As(S₂NC₇H₅CH₃)].

Fig. 5. Antibacterial activity against *Bacillus subtilis*, (1) DMSO, (2) Kanamycin, (3) chloroarsenic(III)dipyrazolinates and (4) [(C₁₅H₁₃N₂O)₂As(S₂NC₇H₅CH₃)].

same antimicrobial effect as compared to Fe^{III} complexes of 3-(2'-hydroxyphenyl)-5-(4'-substituted phenyl)-pyrazoline and aspartic acid³⁵.

Antifungal activity of As^{III} complexes exhibit comparable effect toward *A. flavus* than pyrazolinates of Cu^{II}, Ni^{II}, Co^{II}³³⁻³⁵. As compared to tin complexes, As^{III} com-

plexes show better activity against *B. subtilis* and comparable to pyrazolinates of Cu^{II}, Ni^{II} and Co^{II}³⁶⁻⁴¹.

It can possibly be concluded that the complexation of substituted arsenic(III) moiety with biologically active pyrazoline ligands results in increased activity of these complexes.

Fig. 7. $[As(C_{15}H_{12}N_2OX)_2(S_2NC_7H_5X')]$

where X = -H, -CH₃, -OCH₃ and -Cl ; X' = -CH₃, -OCH₃

Experimental

Solvents (ethanol, acetone and benzene) were rigorously dried and purified by standard methods before use⁴². All the chemicals used were of analytical grade quality and used without further purification. Arsenic trichloride was used as received. Dichloroarsenic(III) [3-(2'-hydroxyphenyl)-5-(4'-substituted phenyl)pyrazolines] and chloroarsenic(III) di[3-(2'-hydroxyphenyl)-5-(4'-substituted phenyl)pyrazolines] were prepared by the reported procedures¹¹. *N*-Aryl dithiocarbamate was synthesized by the reported method⁴³.

Synthesis of $AsCl(C_{15}H_{12}N_2OX)(S_2NC_7H_5X')$:

Newly mixed ligand complexes of arsenic(III) of the general formula $AsCl(C_{15}H_{12}N_2OX)(C_{20}H_{13}ClNO_2)$ were prepared by the reaction of dichloroarsenic(III)pyrazolines and the sodium salt of *N*-aryl dithiocarbamate in 1 : 1 molar ratio.

where X = -H, -CH₃, -OCH₃ and -Cl and X' = -CH₃, -OCH₃

Freshly cut pieces of sodium (0.11 g; 5.2 mmol) were taken in a flask with excess of isopropanol and refluxed

for 30 min, till a clear solution of sodium isopropoxide was obtained. The solution of 3-(2'-hydroxyphenyl)-5-(4'-substituted phenyl)pyrazoline (1.23 g; 5.2 mmol) in anhydrous benzene was then added and the reaction mixture was further refluxed for 30 min, giving a constant light yellow coloured solution. The reaction mixture was cooled to room temperature and then benzene solution of arsenic trichloride (0.94 mL; 5.2 mmol) was added to it with constant stirring. The reaction mixture was further stirred at room temperature for 2 h, till the colour of the reaction mixture become pale yellow. Reaction mixture was filtered to remove precipitated NaCl. The solvent was removed under reduced pressure from the filtrate. The pale yellow coloured solid thus obtained was dissolved in a small amount of acetone. The solution was kept for three days at room temperature. 1.64 g (82%) of compound is formed (m.p. 165 °C).

Methanolic solution of ammonium salt of *N*-aryl dithiocarbamate (0.66 g; 4.0 mmol) was taken in a round bottom flask and added dropwise methanolic solution of the arsenic(III)pyrazolines (1.54 g; 4.0 mmol) formed in the step first with constant stirring. The reaction mixture was stirred for 8 h. After that reaction mixture was filtered to remove precipitated NH₄Cl (0.18 g) and filtrate was dried under vacuum. The light brown colored solid thus obtained was recrystallized in acetone at room temperature. The solid thus precipitated was filtered and dried

Table 7. Antiviral activity of $[AsCl(C_{15}H_{12}N_2OX)(S_2NC_7H_5X')]$ and $[As(C_{15}H_{12}N_2OX)_2(S_2NC_7H_5X')]$

Compd. No.	Compounds	Inhibition
1	$[(C_{15}H_{13}N_2O)As(S_2NC_7H_5CH_3)Cl]$	74.00
2	$[(C_{15}H_{12}N_2OCl)As(S_2NC_7H_5CH_3)Cl]$	65.12
3	$[(C_{15}H_{13}N_2O)As(S_2NC_7H_5OCH_3)Cl]$	60.48
4	$[(C_{15}H_{12}N_2OCH_3)As(S_2NC_7H_5OCH_3)Cl]$	72.10
5	$[(C_{15}H_{12}N_2OCl)As(S_2NC_7H_5OCH_3)Cl]$	75.12
6	$[(C_{15}H_{13}N_2O)_2As(S_2NC_7H_5CH_3)]$	71.36
7	$[(C_{15}H_{12}N_2OCH_3)_2As(S_2NC_7H_5CH_3)]$	64.56
8	$[(C_{15}H_{12}N_2OCl)_2As(S_2NC_7H_5CH_3)]$	62.35
9	$[(C_{15}H_{13}N_2O)_2As(S_2NC_7H_5OCH_3)]$	75.34
10	$[(C_{15}H_{12}N_2OCH_3)_2As(S_2NC_7H_5OCH_3)]$	54.22
11	$[(C_{15}H_{12}N_2OCl)_2As(S_2NC_7H_5OCH_3)]$	75.00

Inhibition calculated by the formula $(C - T)/T \times 100$, where C and T are number of local lesions on control and treated leaves respectively.

in vacuum. 1.60 g, 80% of $[(C_{15}H_{13}N_2O)As-(S_2NC_7H_5CH_3)]Cl$ was obtained. Compound **2-8** were prepared by the same method. The analytical results are presented in Table 1.

Synthesis of $As(C_{15}H_{12}N_2OX)_2(S_2NC_7H_5X')$:

Newly mixed ligand complexes of arsenic(III) of the general formula $As(C_{15}H_{12}N_2OX)_2(S_2NC_7H_5X')$ were prepared by the reaction of chloroarsenic(III)dipyrzolinates and the sodium salt of (*N*-aryl dithiocarbamate) in 1 : 1 molar ratio.

where X = -H, -CH₃, -OCH₃ and -Cl and X' = -CH₃, -OCH₃

Freshly cut pieces of sodium (0.07 g; 3.2 mmol) were taken in a flask with excess of isopropanol and refluxed for 30 min, till a clear solution of sodium isopropoxide was obtained. The solution of 3-(2'-hydroxyphenyl)-5-(4'-substituted phenyl)pyrazolines (0.81 g; 3.2 mmol) in anhydrous benzene was then added and the reaction mixture was further refluxed for 30 min giving a light yellow colour solution. The reaction mixture was cooled to room temperature and then benzene solution of anhydrous AsCl₃ (0.62 mL; 3.2 mmol) was added to it with constant stirring. The reaction mixture was further stirred at room temperature for 2 h, till the colour of the reaction mixture become dark yellow. Reaction mixture was filtered to remove precipitated NaCl (0.18 g), the clear filtrate was dried in vacuum pump. The dark yellow colored solid thus obtained was recrystallized in acetone at room temperature. 1.48 g (74%) of compound was formed (m.p. 190 °C).

Methanolic solution of ammonium salt of *N*-aryl dithiocarbamate (0.47 g; 2.8 mmol) was taken in a round bottom flask and added dropwise methanolic solution of the arsenic(III)dipyrzolinates (1.67 g; 2.8 mmol) formed in the step first with constant stirring. The reaction mixture was stirred for 9 h. After that reaction mixture was filtered to remove precipitated NH₄Cl (0.18 g) and filtrate was dried under vacuum. The dark brown coloured solid thus obtained was recrystallized in acetone at room temperature. The solid thus precipitated was filtered and dried in vacuum. 1.60 g, 80% of $[(C_{15}H_{13}N_2O)_2As-$

$(S_2NC_7H_5CH_3)]$ was obtained. Compound **10-16** was prepared by the same method. The analytical results are presented in Table 1.

Physical measurements :

Chloride was estimated volumetrically by Volhard's method⁴² and arsenic was estimated iodometrically⁴². Messenger's method⁴² was used to estimate the sulphur. Infrared spectra were recorded on Varian 3100 FT-IR spectrophotometer in the range 4000–200 cm⁻¹. The ¹H NMR spectra and proton decoupled ¹³C NMR spectra were recorded at room temperature in CDCl₃ on JEOL AL 300 FT NMR spectrometer, operated at 300.1 and 74.45 MHz, using TMS (tetramethylsilane) as internal standard. The elemental analysis (C, H and N) was obtained by using a Coleman CHN analyzer. The specific optical rotations were recorded at 25 °C in benzene on Perkin-Elmer polarimeter (model 341) using the sodium D line (λ = 589 nm). The FAB mass spectra were recorded on a JEOL SX 102/DA-6000 mass spectrometer. Electronic spectra were recorded in benzene solution on Hitachi U-2000 UV-Visible spectrophotometer.

Antimicrobial studies :

Agar disc diffusion technique was used for screening *in vitro* antimicrobial activity⁴⁴. Inoculums of bacteria were prepared in nutrient broth and fungi in potato dextrose agar slant. The cultures were inoculated and incubated for 48 h in case of bacteria and 5 days in case of fungi. Molten Muller Hinton medium was poured in a sterile Petridis (9 cm in diameter) to get a depth of 5 mm. The medium was left to solidify and then seeded with respective test organisms. For the purpose of seeding, 5 ml sterile water was added to agar slant culture of fungi. The culture was scraped to get a suspension of fungi spore. A sterile cotton swab was dipped in the culture/suspension and lightly rubbed over the solidified medium. The plate was left for a few minutes and then used for the test. 30 μm of each sample to be tested was dissolved in 1 ml acetone. 5 mm discs of Whatman filter paper No. 40 were cut and sterilized. The filter paper discs were immersed in the solution of sample; after soaking, the disc was removed and left in a sterile Petridis to permit the solvent to evaporate. After about 10 min, the paper discs were transferred to seeded agar plate. Discs were kept on

the seeded agar plates. Finally the dishes were incubated at 37 °C for 24 h (for bacteria) and at 30 °C for 72 h (for fungi), where clear or inhibition zones were detected around each disc.

A disc soaked in dimethylsulphoxide alone was used as a control under the same conditions and there was no inhibition zone. Each distinct inhibition zone was measured as diameter in mm, both antibacterial and antifungal activity was calculated as a mean of three replicates.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to SAIF, CDRI, Lucknow (India) and Banaras Hindu University, Varanasi (India) for providing the necessary spectral and analytical data.

References

1. K. H. Antman, *Oncologist*, 2001, **6** (Suppl. 2), 1.
2. W. H. Miller, H. M. Schipper, J. S. Lee, J. Singer and S. Waxman, *Cancer Res.*, 2002, **62**, 3893.
3. P. J. Dilda and P. J. Hogg, *Cancer Treat. Rev.*, 2007, **33**, 542.
4. R. G. Mastin, U.S. 2, 25 A075 Nov, 16 (1961) (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1983, **43**, 11782).
5. J. R. Shah and N. R. Shah, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1982, **21**, 312.
6. J. R. Shah, S. K. Das and R. P. Patel, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1973, **50**, 228.
7. N. R. Shah and J. R. Shah, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1981, **43**, 1593.
8. Fuji Photo Film Ltd., Jpn. K Okai Tokyo Japan, 81, 40, 825 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1982, **96**, 190611).
9. G. Kleefeld and S. Dulzmann, EP 409,026 (Ci.C07D-231/06), (1991).
10. D. J. Greenblat and S. Halder, "Benzodiazepines in Clinical practice", North Holland Publishing Corp., Amsterdam, 1974, **18**.
11. U. N. Tripathi, Mohd. Safi Ahmad, J. S. Solanki and A. Bhardwaj, *J. Coord. Chem.*, 2009, **62**, 636.
12. U. N. Tripathi, J. S. Solanki, A. Bhardwaj and T. R. Thapak, *J. Coord. Chem.*, 2008, **61**, 4025.
13. U. N. Tripathi, Mohd. Safi Ahmad, J. S. Solanki, A. Bhardwaj and A. Siddiqui, *Turk. J. Chem.*, 2009, **33**, 257.
14. U. N. Tripathi, G. Venubabu, Mohd. Safi Ahmad, S. S. R. Kolisetty and A. K. Srivastava, *J. Appl. Organomet. Chem.*, 2006, **20**, 669.
15. U. N. Tripathi, Mohd. Safi Ahmad, G. Venubabu and D. R. Khate, *Main Group Met. Chem.*, 2006, **29**, 39.
16. U. N. Tripathi, Mohd. Safi Ahmad, G. Venubabu and P. J. Ramakrishna, *J. Coord. Chem.*, 2007, **60**, 1777.
17. U. N. Tripathi, Mohd. Safi Ahmad, G. Venubabu and P. J. Ramakrishna, *J. Coord. Chem.*, 2007, **60**, 1709.
18. U. N. Tripathi, Mohd. Safi Ahmad and G. Venubabu, *Turk J. Chem.*, 2007, **31**, 45.
19. K. V. Sharma, Vandana Sharma and U. N. Tripathi, *J. Coord. Chem.*, 2009, **62**, 506.
20. K. V. Sharma, Vandana Sharma and U. N. Tripathi, *J. Coord. Chem.*, 2009, **62**, 1846.
21. K. V. Sharma, Vandana Sharma and U. N. Tripathi, *J. Coord. Chem.*, 2009, **62**, 493.
22. K. V. Sharma, Vandana Sharma, R. K. Dubey and U. N. Tripathi, *J. Coord. Chem.*, 2008, **61**, 3314.
23. K. Nakamoto, "Infrared and Raman spectra of Inorganic and coordination compounds", Wiley Interscience, New York, 1998, pp. 228-232.
24. H. P. S. Chauhan, G. Srivastava and R. C. Mehrotra, *Polyhedron*, 1983, **2**, 359.
25. S. Sharma, R. Sharma, K. Rai, K. Audhek and S. Singh, *Heteroatom Chemistry*, 2004, **15**, 1.
26. H. P. S. Chauhan and U. P. Singh, *App. Organomet. Chem.*, 2007, **21**, 880.
27. R. Ceo-Olivares, J. G. Alvarado, G. Espinosa-Perez, C. Silvestru and I. Haiduc, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1994, 1881.
28. S. S. Garje and V. K. Jain, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 2003, **236**, 35.
29. F. M. N. Kheiri, C. A. Tsipis *et al.*, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1979, **57**.
30. H. P. S. Chauhan, Kavita Kori, Nagulu Meera Shaik, Sanjay Mathur and Volker Huch, *Polyhedron*, 2005, **24**, 89.
31. R. Cea-Olivares, R. Alfredo Toscano, C. Silvestru, P. Garcia-Garcia, M. Lopez-Cardoso, G. Blass-Amador and H. Noth, *J. Organomet. Chem.*, 1995, **497**, 61.
32. R. M. Silverstein and F. X. Webster, "Spectrometric Identification of Organic Compounds", 6th ed., John Wiley & Sons Inc., New York, 1998.
33. U. N. Tripathi, K. V. Sharma, A. Chaturvedi and T. C. Sharma, *Polish J. Chem.*, 2003, **77**, 109.
34. N. Saha and D. K. Sau, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 2005, **30**, 532.
35. A. Siddiqui, Kajal Singh, Kanchan Lata Singh, Shailendra Kumar Gupta, Mohd. Safi Ahmad and U. N. Tripathi, *Appl. Organomet. Chem.*, DOI 10.1002/aoc.2835, 2012.
36. K. V. Sharma, Vandana Sharma and U. N. Tripathi, *J. Coord. Chem.*, 2009, **62**, 506.
37. K. V. Sharma, Vandana Sharma and U. N. Tripathi, *J. Coord. Chem.*, 2009, **62**, 676.
38. K. V. Sharma, Vandana Sharma, R. K. Dubey and U.

- N. Tripathi, *J. Coord. Chem.*, 2009, **62**, 493.
39. U. N. Tripathi, G. Venubabu, Mohd. Safi Ahmad, S. Kolisetty, S. Rao and A. K. Srivastava, *Appl. Organomet. Chem.*, 2006, **20**, 669.
40. U. N. Tripathi, G. Venubabu, Mohd. Safi Ahmad and P. Ramakrishnan, *J. Coord. Chem.*, 2007, **60**, 1709.
41. U. N. Tripathi, G. Venubabu, Mohd. Safi Ahmad and P. Ramakrishnan, *J. Coord. Chem.*, 2007, **60**, 1777.
42. O. C. Monteiro, T. Trindade, J. H. Park and P. O. Breen, *Chem. Vapor Depo.*, 2000, **6**, 230.
43. J. H. Benson, "Microbiological Application", 5th ed., W.M.C. Brown Publication, Oxford, 1990.